

Assessing the Environmental Impact of Bolivia's Energy Transition Using Input-Output Analysis with the MARIO

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- Keywords

Electricity, Energy, CO2 emissions, Environmental Impact, MARIO, IOT, SUT

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Executive Summary

Many countries are actively pursuing energy transitions to reduce their reliance on fossil fuels, and Bolivia is no exception. As a developing country in South America, Bolivia is in the process of transitioning its energy sector towards renewable sources, with the goal of increasing the share of clean energy in its electricity matrix to 79% by 2050. Currently, the country's electricity generation relies heavily on natural gas (69.59%), and faces challenges such as declining gas reserves and the importation of fuels. Using MARIO for impact assesment, this study examines the environmental impacts of the energy transition, employing Input-Output (I-O) tables to model the effects of various scenarios up to 2050.

The methodology used involves constructing Bolivia's Supply and Use Table for 2014 with data from CEPAL and supplementing it with CO2 emissions data from EXIOBASE. Projections indicate that by 2050, renewable energies, particularly hydroelectric and photovoltaic systems, will account for 99% of the installed capacity, significantly reducing CO2 emissions from electricity generation and decreasing dependence on fossil fuels.

Results show that the transition to renewable energy will reduce CO₂ emissions by 1.596 Mton by 2050, primarily due to a shift away from thermal power generation. However, increases in sectors such as construction are observed due to the need for materials for renewable energy infrastructure. While emissions in the electricity sector are expected to decrease, other sectors, such as transportation, will continue to contribute to emissions. The transportation sector remains the most critical in the country.

It is recommended that Bolivia implement policies to support this transition, such as fiscal incentives for clean energy, infrastructure development, and workforce training, in order to reduce fossil fuel dependence, promote a green economy, and mitigate environmental impacts.

1. Introduction

Bolivia is a developing country in South America that is gradually beginning its energy transition towards renewable technologies. The country's electricity matrix is currently dominated by the use of natural gas, which accounts for 69.59% of total electricity generation [1]. Additionally, Bolivia imports fuels such as gasoline and diesel to meet the domestic demand for automobile fuel and electricity generation [2]. These fuels—gas, gasoline, and diesel—are subsidized by more than 40% of their cost for the final consumer [3]. Moreover, in recent years, the country has faced a continuous decline in its natural gas reserves. These issues have led the government to explore renewable technologies to meet the country's energy demand, with the primary goal of increasing the share of renewables to 79% of total power generation by 2050 [4], [5].

The energy transition in Bolivia brings with it various opportunities; however, it also presents different economic and environmental impacts across multiple sectors [6], [7]. To analyze these changes, this study employs an Input-Output-based impact assessment using MARIO, employing Input-Output (I-O) tables provide a valuable tool for understanding the economic and environmental repercussions of activities on sustainability and identifying opportunities for improvement. MARIO enhances this by efficiently processing large volumes of data, offering a scalable and agnostic approach to I-O modeling. It enables users to adopt any type of I-O table, whether single-region or multi-region, and facilitates advanced modifications such as aggregation and scenario creation for evaluating the economic and environmental impacts of policies and processes [8], [9]. This makes MARIO a powerful tool for analyzing complex systems while avoiding slow and recursive operations, thus enabling more effective sustainability analysis.

2. Methodology

The methodology used to determine the environmental effects of the energy transition by 2050, with 2014 as the base year, is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Methodology

Note: EE = Electric Energy

To construct the Supply and Use Table (SUT) for Bolivia, it was employed Input-Output Tables for Latin America and the Caribbean provided by CEPAL [10]. These tables capture the interactions between 35 sectors of the Bolivian economy for 2014:

- | | |
|---|---|
| S1: Non-Industrial Agricultural Products | S19: Petroleum Refining Products |
| S2: Industrial Agricultural Products | S20: Non-Metallic Mineral Products |
| S3: Coca | S21: Basic Metal Products |
| S4: Livestock Products | S22: Metal Products, Machinery, and Equipment |
| S5: Forestry, Hunting, and Fishing | S23: Miscellaneous Manufactured Products |
| S6: Crude Oil and Natural Gas | S24: Electricity, Gas, and Water |
| S7: Metallic and Non-Metallic Minerals | S25: Construction |
| S8: Fresh and Processed Meats | S26: Trade |
| S9: Dairy Products | S27: Transportation and Storage |
| S10: Milling and Bakery Products | S28: Communications |
| S11: Sugar and Confectionery | S29: Financial Services |
| S12: Miscellaneous Food Products | S30: Business Services |
| S13: Beverages | S31: Residential Property |
| S14: Processed Tobacco | S32: Community, Social, and Personal Services |
| S15: Textiles, Garments, and Leather Products | S33: Restaurants and Hotels |
| S16: Wood and Wood Products | S34: Domestic Services |
| S17: Paper and Paper Products | S35: Public Administration Services |
| S18: Chemicals and Chemical Products | |

However, this dataset does not include information on CO₂ emissions. To address this gap, the study supplemented the data with information from EXIOBASE, a comprehensive global database on economic relations, international trade, and environmental footprints, with a particular focus on Latin American data [11]. Additionally, a correction for CO₂ emissions was developed, considering that Bolivia's energy sector is predominantly reliant on natural gas. This adjustment was based on data from *Our World in Data*, which reports

CO₂ emissions from the electricity sector at 4.63 million tons (Mton) and from the transport sector at 8.81Mton tons for Bolivia [12].

The sector S24: Electricity, Gas, and Water is the principal focus of this study however its just consider the electric change not the gas and water. The electric power generation capacity and distribution for the base scenario (2014) were obtained from the *Anuario Estadístico de Energía Eléctrica 2014* [13]. For the decarbonization scenarios (2030, 2035, 2040, 2045, and 2050), the data were sourced from a study by Jiménez et al. (2025)[14], which incorporated all future government plans outlined in the National Energy Plan [15], [16], using the Energy Scope model. As shown in Figure 2, in 2014, thermoelectric plants powered by natural gas dominated the electricity matrix. Projections for subsequent years suggest a gradual increase in installed electrical capacity, with renewables expected to make up as much as 99% of the energy mix by 2050. This shift to renewable energy not only transforms the country’s energy matrix but also reduces environmental impacts, boosts investment in certain sectors, and decreases the reliance on fossil fuels. In this context, the economic values for the decarbonization scenarios—such as CAPEX and CO₂ emissions—were also derived from the study by Jiménez et al. (2025)[14].

Figure 2: Power Capacity Distribution in Bolivia

Note: 2014= 2.21GW, 2025=3.97GW, 2030=6.39GW, 2035=8.20GW, 2040=12.66GW, 2045=15.36, 2050=18.68 GW
 Source: Jimenez et al. 2025 (Energy Scope Bolivia model)

The CAPEX value is allocated between S22: Metallic Products, Machinery, and Equipment, and S25: Construction. Additionally, the impact of electricity generation is considered, particularly from sectors such as S6: Crude Oil and Natural Gas, and S19: Petroleum Refining Products. This is due to the use of natural gas and diesel as fuels in thermoelectric plants (CCGT, OCGT, and ST_SNG), as well as the use of diesel in diesel generators (GENSET_DIESEL). The values for these sectors are derived from Jiménez et al. (2025), based on the differences in installed capacity relative to the base year. Finally, the MARIO was used to perform an Input-Output-based Impacts Assessment which determine the environmental impacts of various energy transition scenarios.

3. Results

Results from the environmental impact (CO₂ emissions) assessment presented in Figure 3 show that transitioning to renewable energy sources for electricity generation leads to a significant reduction in CO₂ emissions compared to 2014. Specifically, the S24: Electricity, Gas, and Water achieves a reduction of 1.596 Mton by 2050 compared to the base year, primarily due to the increased electricity generation from renewable sources, particularly hydropower and photovoltaic (PV) systems. The S6: Crude Oil and Natural Gas shows a reduction of 0.026 Mton by 2050, driven by a decreased reliance on natural gas for electricity generation. Additionally, S19: Petroleum Refining Products sees a reduction of 0.005 Mton by 2050, mainly due to the reduced use of diesel.

These reductions are mainly attributed to the significant increase in renewable power generation and the corresponding decrease in the use of thermal power plants and diesel generators. As shown in Figure 2, it is expected that by 2050, diesel generators will be eliminated, and thermal power plants will be reduced by up to 0.79%. Meanwhile, the installed capacity of renewable energy sources is expected to increase by 99.23%.

However, an increase is also observed in all sectors due to the energy transition in electricity generation each year compared to 2014. The largest increases until 2050 are seen in sector S20: Non-Metallic Mineral Products, which experiences an increase of 0.07 Mton, followed by S22: Metal Products, Machinery, and Equipment with an increase of 0.026 Mton, S21: Basic Metal Products with an increase of 0.022 Mton, and S25: Construction with an increase of 0.002 Mton. These increases are mainly driven by the use of different materials in construction, such as metals, aggregates, and construction work (e.g., land conditioning), which will be required for the development and expansion of renewable energy technologies in Bolivia.

Figure 3: CO2 Emissions reduction from 2014 to different years.

Upon analyzing the total emissions per year shown in Figure 4, it is evident that the reduction compared to the base year 2014 is decreasing, with the most significant decrease occurring in 2040, when renewable installed capacity reaches 83%. Emissions reduce by 0.349 Mton in 2030, by 0.311 Mton in 2035, by 1.507 Mton in 2040, by 1.486 Mton in 2045, and by 1.483 Mton in 2050 compared to 2014. However, the S27: Transportation and Storage sector remains the highest emitter of CO₂ across the country, showing an increase in emissions each year. By 2050, emissions from this sector are expected to increase in 0.0072 Mton compared with the base year. This sector is one of the most critical in the country, primarily due to Bolivia's fuel subsidy, which reduces fuel prices by more than 40% for both the transportation and power generation sectors. This subsidy makes fuel use more attractive and cost-effective for end users, leading to an increase in the transport sector's emissions.

Figure 4: CO₂ Emissions per year.

4. Discussion

Bolivia’s transition to renewable energy presents substantial opportunities to reduce CO₂ emissions, mitigate environmental impact, and reduce reliance on fossil fuels. By 2050, the electricity sector is expected to decrease CO₂ emissions by 1.596 Mton, largely through the integration of hydropower and photovoltaic systems. However, while emissions from the energy sector are set to decline, other sectors, such as construction, will experience an increase due to the demand for materials needed for renewable energy infrastructure.

This underscores the importance of a comprehensive approach to energy transition, one that not only focuses on emissions reductions in the electricity sector but also addresses the environmental impacts in construction and manufacturing. Impact Assessments for renewable technologies like hydropower have shown that environmental impact reductions depend on factors such as the lifespan of technology and its electricity generation capacity. These studies also highlight that the greatest environmental impacts typically occur during the construction phase, as it involves significant land changes and the use of a variety of materials, further emphasizing the need for sustainable building practices throughout the transition process [17], [18]

Although Bolivia is making progress in reducing emissions through the growth of renewable energy in the electricity sector, the transportation sector continues to be a major challenge. The fuel subsidy, which lowers prices by over 40%, makes fuel more affordable and encourages increased transportation demand, leading to higher emissions. This creates a contradiction in the country's emission reduction goals. For real progress, it's essential to rethink fuel subsidies and invest in cleaner transportation technologies to avoid undermining the achievements in other sectors.

The study has limitations, such as assuming energy transition impacts are limited to the electricity sector and not fully accounting for indirect effects on other sectors. It also lacks detailed analysis of social and economic impacts, especially on vulnerable populations.

Future research could address these gaps by studying the socio-economic effects of energy transition policies on local communities and employment, exploring emerging renewable technologies, evaluate the gas employment in different areas and assessing the implementation challenges in Bolivia's unique socio-political context.

5. Conclusion

Bolivia's transition to renewable energy presents significant opportunities to reduce CO2 emissions, especially in the electricity sector, where a 1.596 Mton reduction is anticipated by 2050. While this shift marks progress in decarbonizing the energy sector, it also brings challenges in sectors such as construction and manufacturing. These industries may face increased emissions due to the growing demand for materials needed for renewable energy infrastructure. Additionally, sectors like S27: Transport and Storage have a major impact on the country. This is largely due to the sector receiving 40% of the fuel subsidy, which has led to an increase in the number of vehicles on the road. Furthermore, the sector also faces ongoing fuel smuggling across borders with neighboring countries. These issues highlight the need for new studies and strategies to address the challenges and drive change in this sector.

To ensure a successful energy transition, it is essential to adopt a holistic policy approach that addresses both direct and indirect emissions across all sectors. The energy transition should not only focus on reducing emissions in the electricity sector but also consider the environmental impacts in industries like construction and manufacturing. A shift towards low-carbon construction is critical; promoting the use of green materials and energy-efficient technologies in renewable infrastructure can significantly reduce emissions in the construction phase, which tends to have the most substantial environmental impact.

Technological diversification is also key. Investing in a broad mix of renewable technologies such as wind, solar, geothermal, and bioenergy will help create a more resilient energy system. In parallel, Bolivia must gradually phase out fossil fuel subsidies to

encourage the adoption of renewable energy while providing support for workers transitioning from fossil fuel industries.

Lastly, ensuring social equity throughout this transition is vital. Job retraining programs and support for affected workers will help mitigate the socio-economic challenges that come with the shift to a low-carbon economy. Bolivia's pathway to a sustainable energy future will require the integration of sound policies, technological innovation, and a focus on social equity to ensure long-term success, environmental sustainability, and a just transition for all its citizens.

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